

Original Article

A Finite Element Study of Lean Anterior Cervical Plating Instrumentation Designs

S.P. Vishnu, K.G.V. Sivakumar*, C.V. Muraleedharan

Department of Medical Devices Engineering, Biomedical Technology Wing, Sree Chitra Tirunal Institute for Medical Science and Technology, Poojapura, Trivandrum 695012, India

Received: 3 May 2024
Accepted: 25 May 2024
Published online: 15 June 2024

Keywords: anterior cervical plating, lean implant design, plate-screw interface, finite element modelling, contact stress, axial screw load

This study reports a finite element model for predicting stresses at the critical locations of an anterior cervical plating instrumentation due to routine neck movements of flexion, extension, lateral bending, axial rotation and a combination thereof. The model's simplicity lies in the remote mapping of the applied moments directly at the anchoring locations of the plating system construct without the complexities of invoking the cervical spinal architecture. The model's utility is demonstrated by evaluating the performance of two different 'lean' plating system designs, viz. 'uniformly lean plate' and 'lean plate-with-stubs'. The axial screw loads were found to be under 150N for all the neck movement cases simulated, well below the pullout force of the screws typically employed in anterior cervical plating systems. The von Mises stress at the critical locations, viz., plate-screw interfaces and screwhead surfaces, was found to be below 150MPa. The contact stress at the anchor locations of the plate with the vertebral body was determined to be 31.8% higher for the 'lean plate-with-stubs' than the 'uniformly lean plate'. The higher contact stress in the former appears to be adequate to induce changes in bone remodelling, favouring osseointegration.

© (2024) Society for Biomaterials & Artificial Organs #20005024

Introduction

Anterior cervical plates (ACP) are slender metallic structures made in conformation with the anterior profile of the cervical spine to provide adequate structural stability after anterior cervical corpectomy, anterior cervical discectomy, and fusion (ACDF) or other trauma-related surgeries [1].

Vertebral shape and structure are bound to change between individuals; hence, fixation of these metallic ACPs on vertebral surfaces necessitates using variable angle screws capable of providing angulations in the longitudinal and transverse directions.

When the screws are highly angulated, the screwhead may protrude outside the ventral surface of the plate, if the plate thickness is not adequate to accommodate the screw inside the screwhead. However, a thicker plate will be stiffer and also increase the likelihood of dysphagia [1], and thus not suited for an excellent plating system.

A lean plate may aid in partial load transfer through the bone [2,3], which promotes bone fusion while minimising the chances of dysphagia. An ideal cervical plate minimises dysphagia and is compliant enough to transfer load partially through the bone while also stiff enough to provide structural stability [2,3].

But, when the plate is leaned by making it thinner, accommodating the screwhead within the plate without the screwhead protrusion at extreme angulations becomes a concern. However, reducing the screwhead thickness may address this issue at the expense of reduced contact area at the plate-screwhead interface, especially at extreme angulations. Comparatively smaller plate thickness at the plate-screw interfering surface and thinner screwhead make those regions critical while designing a lean plate.

After implantation and during routine cervical spine movements, viz. flexion, extension, lateral bending, and axial rotation, the resulting moments impose axial loads on the screws and, in turn, the plate [1,4]. Because the load gets transmitted to the plate via the screws, each movement accounts for stress development on the plate and the screws. It is necessary to find out the resulting

* Corresponding author
E-mail address: sivakumar@scimst.ac.in (Dr. K.G.V. Sivakumar)

stress distribution in the plate, screws, and the plate-screw interface, for developing the plating system design. One possible way to find these stress values is by modelling a cervical spine with discs and ligaments from C1 to C7, attaching the spinal instrumentation to the validated spinal model, and applying necessary moments [5], as reported in the literature. However, this modelling method better approximates the actual scenario; a different modelling strategy is employed here to optimise spinal instrumentation, a different modelling strategy involving remote mapping of load and moment impulses directly onto the spinal instrumentation. This approach simplifies the model geometry greatly by preventing the use of cervical spinal elements such as vertebral bodies, discs, and ligaments. It represents the worst-case situation whereby the entire applied load or moment impulses act directly on the spinal instrumentation, whereas in reality, only a portion of the applied load will act upon the construct. Such a model engine helps compare spinal instrumentation sets for iterative design optimisation.

Materials and Methods

In this study, material properties of heat-treated Ti6Al4V, presented in our previous study, are used for modelling and are shown in table 1 [6]. The present study proposes two independent cervical plate designs: lean plate-with-stubs (LPS) and uniformly lean plate (ULP). Details of the design features are discussed below.

Lean plate-with-stubs (LPS)

A three-dimensional CAD model of a 2-level anterior cervical plate 46mm long and 16mm wide is shown in figure 1(a). The plate is of 1.2mm thickness except at the stubs, where an additional standoff of 0.8mm is provided to make it 2mm thick. Stubs are provided on the dorsal surface of the plate at the ends as well as at the central position. Comparatively higher thickness of the plate at the stub region enables the designing screws of larger head and

shaft dimensions, which improves the contact area between the screwhead and screwhole surface, which may help reduce the formation of the high-stress region at the plate-hole interface. The plate is designed with lordotic and transverse curvatures of 165 and 32 mm, respectively. Screwholes are designed so that screws can be angulated to a maximum of 15° cephalad in the sagittal plane and 6° medial in the transverse plane [7]. Screwhole trajectories are designed to ensure a minimum contact of at least 0.5mm at the plate-screw interface, even at the extreme angulation of 15°. The screwhead is chamfered to ensure no head protrusion above the plate surface at all possible screw angulations.

Uniformly lean plate (ULP)

A plate of 1.6mm uniform thickness, 16mm wide and 46mm long with transverse and lordotic curvatures similar to the previous design as shown in figure 1(b). The shaft diameter of the screw was reduced to 3.5mm to achieve the same screw angulations as in the LPS design, retaining the exact screwhead dimensions. Screwholes are suitably modified to accommodate the newly designed screwhead and achieve the angulations. As a result of these modifications, the minimum contact length at the plate-screwhead interface reduced to 0.3mm at the extreme angulations.

Finite element modeling

Finite element modelling of the plate-screw construct was conducted using ANSYS Workbench 18.2, formulated as a non-linear mechanical problem solved in the Static Structural module [8]. This study aims to determine the stress development at the screwhole interface of the plating system in response to moment impulses caused by neck movement. The model geometry consisted of a cervical plate with four screws (figure 2) C, D, E, and F without threaded shafts, inserted into the screwholes in such a way that all the four screws have both 15° cephalad or caudal (Y-Z plane of the global coordinate system) and 6° medial (X-Z plane) angulations to make the construct modelled for the limiting angulation scenario as shown in figure 2.

The following assumptions were made while modelling the construct.

1. Moments applied at the remote points act entirely on the construct without any loss.
2. The plate is fixed at the centre of the dorsal surface, i.e. at the middle stub region.

A remote mapping strategy was used here, as mentioned previously, by defining a remote point P having coordinates (0 mm, 27.5 mm, 8.5mm) with respect to a new coordinate system located at the centroid of the plate (centre of S2 in figure 2) [1]. The remote point P represents what would have been the centre of the superior surface of the top vertebral body to which the cervical plate is affixed. It is at the remote point location where the moments

Figure 1: 3D CAD model of a lean plate-with-stub (LPS) and a uniformly lean plate (ULP); (a) LPS dorsal surface (opposite face is referred to as ventral surface); (b) ULP (dorsal surface)

Table 1: Material property data of Ti6Al4V

Ti6Al4V (heat-treated)	
Young's modulus (Gpa)	120
Poisson ratio	0.3
True stress, $\sigma_{0.2\%}$ (Mpa)	960
True stress, σ_{UTS} (Mpa)	1182

Figure 2: Dorsal surface of LPS showing (i) fixed support provided at the S2 stub surface (shown in blue colour) (ii) Remote point P mapped to the S1 and S3 stub surfaces (shown in red colour) represented schematically via straight lines (iii) force A and moment B acted up on remote point P (iv) screw heads with the corresponding coordinate systems named C, D, E and F and a local coordinate system located at the centroid of the plate

corresponding to the neck movement and force due to the weight of the head act upon. The equivalent components are mapped to the dorsal surface of two end stubs (S1 and S3, figure 2). Remote boundary condition provides means to apply loads anywhere in space, and the equivalent moments and forces will directly be applied to the mapped body by rigid connection [9].

Boundary conditions

A remote displacement boundary condition was applied to the screw surfaces, as shown in figure 2, by defining local coordinate systems at points C, D, E, and F at the bottom surfaces of the four screws. Translation and rotation along the screw axis (X-axis) were arrested while allowing the rest of the translation and rotation movements. A fixed support condition was specified at the middle stub region at the dorsal surface marked as location 'G' in figure 2.

The rationale for selecting the above boundary condition in the model is based on replicating the actual scenario where the plate is fixed to the vertebral bodies. In reality, all four screws at the anchoring locations, along with vertebral bodies, move as a single unit when the cervical spine turns as a result of neck movement, with the exception of axial screw rotation and translation.

The current boundary conditions, while permitting the permissible screw movements as described above, allow for the calculation of stresses at the screwhole interface from impulse. To ensure model convergence while addressing these boundary conditions, a fixation point was necessary. The central portion of the middle stub (denoted as point G) was chosen as the fixation point because it was observed not to hinder screw movement caused by moment impulses. While the choice of this fixation is expected to alter the stress prediction at the centre of the cervical plate, model predictions of stress at the plate-screw interfaces, which are further away from the plate center, are of interest in the present study.

The same set of boundary conditions was applied in the lean plate

model as well by splitting the dorsal surface of the plate into regions the same as before, such as S1, S2, and S3. The contact between the screwhead and screwhole is treated as a frictional contact with a coefficient of friction of 0.3 [10,11] and was formulated using Augmented Lagrange formulation [12]. Symmetric behaviour was chosen to model the contact to avoid interpenetration of contacting surfaces.

A static downward force of 80N (represented as **A**) and a counterclockwise moment of 1.5Nm [2] (represented as **B**) were applied at the remote point P about the Y axis via the global coordinate system to represent the weight of the head and axial rotation movement of the neck respectively as shown in figure 2. Studies show that moments typically generated during neck movement usually fall from 1 to 3 Nm [4,13-15]. Similarly, 1.5Nm clockwise and counterclockwise moments were applied about the X-axis to model flexion and extension. A counterclockwise moment of 1.5Nm about the Z axis was applied to model lateral bending. Simultaneous application of counterclockwise moments of 1.5Nm about the X, Y, and Z axes was employed to model an extreme worst-case scenario, referred to as the combined impulse case.

The application of moment through remote mapping results in the entire load acting on the plating system elements, unlike the actual scenario where the cervical spinal architecture will likely bear a fraction of the applied load. However, for design optimisation of the plating system elements, the present approach is satisfactory as they are likely to be somewhat overdesigned, thus significantly reducing the risk of failure during service. This simplification allows for a detailed stress analysis at the plate-screw hole interface without complex modelling of the cervical spinal architecture.

Meshing

The plate and screwhead were meshed in quadratic order with tetrahedron elements of Solid 187, which is a 10-node element and is best suited for irregularly shaped objects [8]. Proximity and

Figure 3: Meshed view of plate and screw, highlighting the use of refined mesh inside the screwhole (locations K and L) and screw (location M), compared to relatively coarser mesh for the plate

Curvature size functions were used, which yielded a uniform mesh at fillets and curved edges of the plate [8]. Critical areas, such as the screwhead and screwhole surface, were refined with a finer mesh by providing face sizing at the corresponding contact faces.

Mesh sensitivity study

A mesh sensitivity study was conducted by varying the element size selectively at the screwholes [8] (K and L) and screwhead surface (M) through the thickness of the plate body (N) separately, as shown in figure 3. Selective mesh refinement was employed due to the intricate nature of the area of interest in this study, specifically the screw hole interface, which comprises minute features. Employing a mesh size smaller than these features would

Table 2: Element sizes used for mesh sensitivity study at locations K, L, M and N (see Fig.3)

Location	K	L	M	N
	1.2	1.2	1.2	1.2
	0.6	0.6	0.6	0.6
	0.4	0.4	0.4	0.4
Element Size (mm)	0.3	0.3	0.3	0.3
	0.2	0.2	0.2	1.2
	0.1	0.1	0.1	1.2
	0.06	0.06	0.06	1.2
	0.05	0.05	0.05	1.2

Figure 4: (a) Plot of equivalent stress versus element size at the locations ‘K’, ‘L’ and ‘M’; (b) Plot of equivalent stress versus element size at ‘N’

(a)LPS screwhead in flexion

(b)LPS screwhead in extension

(c)LPS screwhead in lateral bending

Figure 5: Stress map and direction of axial screw load on the screw head surfaces labelled H1, H2, H3, and H4 for flexion, extension, axial rotation, lateral bending, and combined moment impulse scenario for LPS (a, b, c, d and e) and combined impulse scenario of ULP (f)

(d)LPS screwhead in axial rotation

(e)LPS screwhead in combined impulse scenario

(f)ULP screwhead in combined impulse scenario

Figure 5: (continued) Stress map and direction of axial screw load on the screw head surfaces labelled H1, H2, H3, and H4 for flexion, extension, axial rotation, lateral bending, and combined moment impulse scenario for LPS (a, b, c, d and e) and combined impulse scenario of ULP (f)

significantly increase the total number of structural elements, rendering the computational complexity impractical. The element sizes are varied from 0.3 to 1.2mm on the entire plate construct. Critical locations consisting of K, L, and M were refined further by reducing element size from 0.3 to 0.05mm. The different combinations of mesh element sizes at locations K, L, M, and N used for the mesh sensitivity study were tabulated in table 2.

Results

Mesh refinement study

The result of the mesh refinement study conducted by varying the element size at regions K, L, M and N (figure 3) are summarized in figure 4. Element-averaged equivalent stress over an area of 0.5mm² at K, L and M and 5mm² at N were used for this study. At location K, the element size refinement from 0.2 to 0.1mm resulted in a relative error of 19.4%. The relative error between successive refinements decreased to 0.65% at 0.06mm and 0.44% at 0.05mm element sizes. Similarly, at location L, the relative error was reduced from 6.4% to 1.5% and then to 0.93%, with the element size reducing from 0.2 to 0.1, 0.1 to 0.06, and 0.06 to 0.05mm, respectively. Location M also showed the relative error reducing from 18.5% to 0.9% and 3.8% when subjected to a similar elemental size reduction. Element size refinements at location N in the 1.2, 0.6, 0.4, and 0.3mm sequence resulted in relative errors of 6, 9.3, and 0.85% between successive refinements.

Based on these results, the element sizes at locations K, L, M, and N were chosen as 0.05, 0.1, 0.1, and 0.4mm, respectively. This choice is justified as the relative errors at these entire locations was well under 5%, with the benefit of saving computational time.

Construct model of LPS and ULP

The results of finite element models with 1.5Nm moment impulses corresponding to flexion, extension, lateral bending, and

axial rotation applied to the plating system are presented below. Screwheads are identified as H1, H2, H3, and H4, as in figure 5, and the same terminology is followed on all the models discussed herein.

During flexion (figure 5a), both H1 and H3 screws experienced an axial screw load of 16N directed outwards. H2 and H4 screws experienced an axial screw load of 32N directed inwards. In extension (figure 5b), an axial screw load of 50N directed outwards acted up on H2 and H4 screws, while 98N acted up on H1 and H3 inwards. Stress at the screwhead surfaces was well below 40MPa.

In lateral bending (figure 5c), the H2 screw experienced an outward axial load of 13N and H4, 20N. An axial inward load of 41N acted upon H1 and 25N upon H3. The H1 and H3 screwheads possess stress values of less than 20MPa (figure 5c).

During axial rotation (figure 5d), an outward axial load of 50N acted upon the H3 screwhead and 90N on the H4 head. H1 and H2 screwheads experienced axially inward loads of 175 and 100N, respectively. The H1 screwhead experienced comparatively higher stress of less than 100MPa.

In the combined impulse scenario, the H3 screwhead experiences an axial outward load of 8.6N, whereas 130N acts on H4. At the same time, H1 and H2 acted by axially inward loads of 257 and 17N, respectively. This resulted in a maximum stress of 130MPa on the H1 screw head surface (figure 5e).

The combined impulse scenario simulated for ULP manifested stresses well below 150MPa, similar to LPS. The plate designs exhibited approximately similar axially inward and outward screw loads with a maximum of 125N outwards and 245N inwards. Stress distribution was also identical to LPS on the screwhead surface, with a high-stress region resting upon the H1 head (figure 5f).

Figure 6: Bar chart showing a comparison of the maximum Von Mises stress at the screwhole interface for the current study and Li et al. for flexion, extension, lateral bending, and axial rotation

DiPaola et al. [16] studied the screw pullout force in the anterior cervical plate construct. They found that for fixed-angle screws, the maximum screw pullout force was 288 ± 37 N and 297 ± 41 N for variable-angle screws. The current model calculated an axially outward force of less than 100N for all individual moment scenarios. The combined impulse scenario also showed only 130N, which is less than half of the maximum screw pullout force of the construct.

Figure 6 shows a bar chart of the maximum von Mises stress formed at the screwhead and screwhole in flexion, extension, lateral bending, and axial rotation. The chart also shows results comparing simulations of hybrid decompression and fusion surgery reported by Li et al. [4]. Their model comprised the entire cervical spine from C2 to C7 vertebrae with the plating instrumentation attached at C3- C5 levels. Further, a fixed support was provided at the bottom surface of C7. An axial compressive load of 73.6N and a moment of 1Nm were applied on the superior surface of C2 to simulate neck movements.

The bar chart shows that stress at the plate-screw interface predicted from the present model was under 100MPa in all cases. In extension, lateral bending and axial rotation stresses were in reasonable agreement with those reported by Li et al. However, a significant difference was observed in flexion.

Discussion

Stress in the plating system

The current study shows that maximum stress prediction at the screwhead interface of the LPS design was below 50MPa in all the moment impulse scenarios. Model of Li et al. predicts higher stress numbers for lateral bending and axial rotation and a significant change for flexion scenarios. Li et al. discuss mainly von Mises stress at the screwhead interface after fixation with the aid of a full vertebral model. Unlike the current model, even with a lower applied moment, Li et al. predicted a higher stress of 95MPa. The difference can likely be attributed to the distinct design features of the screwhead and screw hole. Specifically, the screw hole appears cylindrical, while the screwhead takes the form of a flange affixed to the top of a cylindrical rod. This peculiar design might create sharp corners on the screw trajectory and may result in higher stress development at the screwhead interface. In this study, this issue was circumvented by using the FE models for iterative enhancement of screwhead and screwhead trajectory designs by systematically eliminating potential areas of high stress concentration away from the screwhead interface. This optimization approach reduces stress on the screwhead interface of the plate designs.

Contact stress at the vertebral bodies

Post-surgical fixation of the cervical plates exerts stress at the contact locations with the vertebral bodies, influenced by routine neck movements. Contact stress is calculated as axial screw load associated with the neck movement divided by the contact area between the plate and the vertebral body. The contact area refers to the area of the cervical plate at the dorsal side that comes in contact with the vertebral body after fixation. Notably, plates with smaller contact areas, such as LPS plates with stubs, exhibit increased contact stress. For instance, compared to ULP plates, LPS plates with stubs show a 23% reduction in the contact area, leading to contact stresses of 4.1MPa and 3.1MPa during axial rotation, respectively, despite experiencing similar axial loads.

Further, optimisation through redesigning the stub profile can reduce the contact area by an additional 40%, resulting in contact

stress of 5.5MPa during axial rotation. The contact stress was calculated from the axial screw load predicted by the model divided by the contact area between the plate and the surface of the vertebral body.

Carter et al. found that changes in cyclic bone stresses of 1 MPa (less than 1 percent of the ultimate strength of the cortical bone) can cause measurable differences in bone remodelling after a few months [17]. The increased contact stress of the LPS design is expected to provide better seating and anchoring of the cervical plate on the vertebral body, thereby creating a favourable condition for bone remodelling and osseointegration [18,19].

Conclusion

Two different lean anterior cervical plating systems were designed: (i) a 1.6mm thick uniformly lean plate (ULP) and (ii) a 1.2mm thick plate with 0.8mm thick stub at anchoring locations (LPS). A finite element model was developed for studying the stresses at the plate-screw hole interface of the anterior cervical plate that could be used for iterative design optimisation by simulating the behaviour of the construct at an approximate implanted condition without a spinal model.

Axial screw loads for the different moment impulse cases studied were found to be below 150N, well below the typical pullout strengths of variable angle screws reported in the literature. Equivalent stress at the plate-screwhead interface for both plate designs was below 150MPa. The contact stress at the anchoring locations between the plate and the vertebral bodies was determined to be 31.8% higher for the LPS design compared to the ULP design, which can further be increased to 77.4% by redesigning the stub profile of LPS. This is expected to produce better anchoring and proper seating of the cervical plate on the vertebral surface, enabling osseointegration. One or both designs of the cervical plates will be chosen based on clinical inputs to fabricate prototypes for *in vitro* testing. Precisely, plate-level and construct-level tests are planned as per ASTM F382 and F1717 standards to evaluate the performance of the plating systems and demonstrate suitability for clinical use.

Acknowledgements

Funding provided by the Department of Science and Technology, Government of India, via the Technical Research Centre (TRC) program initiative is acknowledged.

References

- Galbusera, F., Wilke, H.J., *Biomechanics of the Spine - Basic Concepts, Spinal Disorders and Treatments* (2018).
- Peterson, J.M., Chlebek, C., Clough, A.M., Wells, A.K., and Ledet, E.H., Stiffness Matters: Part I-The Effects of Plate Stiffness on the Biomechanics of ACDF in Vitro, *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)*, **43**(18), E1061–E1068 (2018).
- Peterson, J.M., Chlebek, C., Clough, A.M., Wells, A.K., Batzinger, K.E., Houston, J.M., Kradinova, K., Glennon, J.C., DiRisio, D.J., Ledet, E.H., Stiffness Matters: Part II-The Effects of Plate Stiffness on Load-Sharing and the Progression of Fusion Following Anterior Cervical Discectomy and Fusion in Vivo, *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)*, **43**(18), E1069–E1076 (2018).
- Brodke, D.S., Klimo, P., Bachus, K.N., Braun, J.T., Dailey, A.T., Anterior Cervical Fixation: Analysis of Load-Sharing and Stability with Use of Static and Dynamic Plates, *J Bone Joint Surg Am*, **88**(7), 1566–1573 (2023).
- Li, Z., Liu, H., Yang, M., and Zhang, W., A Biomechanical Analysis of Four Anterior Cervical Techniques to Treating Multilevel Cervical Spondylotic Myelopathy: A Finite Element Study, *BMC Musculoskeletal Disorders*, **22**(1), 278 (2021).
- Siva Kumar, K.G.V., Mohammed, A.T., Rajeev, A., Muraleedharan, C.V., Finite Element Study of Bending of a Custom 2-Level Anterior Cervical Plate in 4-Point Configuration, *Trans Indian Natl. Acad. Eng.*

- 8(2), 263–272 (2023).
7. Moftakhar, R., Trost, G.R., Anterior Cervical Plates: A Historical Perspective, *Neurosurg Focus*, **16**(1), p. E8 (2004).
 8. Lee, H.H., *Finite Element Simulations with ANSYS Workbench 2023: Theory, Applications, Case Studies*, SDC Publications (2023).
 9. Remote Boundary Conditions and Constraint Equations: Introduction To ANSYS Mechanical Equations Mechanics, [Online]. Available: <https://www.scribd.com/document/395318674/Liberman>. [Accessed: 23-Aug-2023].
 10. Faure, L., Bolle, B., Philippon, S., Schuman, C., Chevrier, P., Tidu, A., Friction Experiments for Titanium Alloy Tribopairs Sliding in Dry Conditions: Sub-Surface and Surface Analysis, *Tribology International*, **Complete** (54), 17–25 (2012).
 11. Sreesha, R.B., Kumar, D., Chandraker, S., Agrawal, A., Room Temperature Sliding Wear Behavior of Ti6Al4V: A Review, 2341, 040041 (2021).
 12. Contact Analysis Best Practices, Ansys Learning Forum | Ansys Innovation Space.
 13. Panjabi, M.M., Isomi, T., and Wang, J.L., Loosening at the Screw-Vertebra Junction in Multilevel Anterior Cervical Plate Constructs,” *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)*, **24**(22), 2383–2388 (1999).
 14. Haghpanahi, M., Javadi, M., A Three Dimensional Parametric Model of Whole Lower Cervical Spine (C3–C7) under Flexion, Extension, Torsion and Lateral Bending, *Scientia Iranica*, **19**(1), 142–150 (2012).
 15. Grubb, M.R., Currier, B.L., Shih, J.S., Bonin, V., Grabowski, J.J., Chao, E.Y., Biomechanical Evaluation of Anterior Cervical Spine Stabilization, *Spine (Phila Pa 1976)*, **23**(8), 886–892 (1998).
 16. DiPaola, C.P., Jacobson, J.A., Awad, H., Conrad, B.P., Reichtine, G.R., Screw Pull-out Force Is Dependent on Screw Orientation in an Anterior Cervical Plate Construct, *J Spinal Disord Tech*, **20**(5), 369–373 (2007).
 17. Carter, D.R., Vasu, R., Harris, W.H., The Plated Femur: Relationships between the Changes in Bone Stresses and Bone Loss, *Acta Orthop Scand*, **52**(3), 241–248 (1981).
 18. Millis, D., Responses of Musculoskeletal Tissues to Disuse and Remobilization, *Canine Rehabilitation and Physical Therapy: Second Edition*, 113–159 (2004).
 19. Fan, Y., Xiu, K., Dong, X., Zhang, M., The Influence of Mechanical Loading on Osseointegration: An Animal Study,” *Sci China C Life Sci*, **52**(6), 579–586 (2000).